

AYRIM CHORVACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI

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Annotasiya Ushbu maqola Samarqand viloyatida 2010-2023 yillarda sut va go'sht ishlab chiqarishning narxi, veterinariya xizmatlari, ish haqi, oziqa birligi uchun qilingan xarajatlar ekonometrik modellar tahlil qilgan. Ushbu omillar sut va go'sht ishlab chiqarishiga ta'siri nazariy-amaliy jihatdan tadqiq qilingan hamda ularning o'zaro ta'siri orasidagi bog'lanish modeli tuzilgan va optimal variant tanlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: regressiya, korrelyatsiya koeffitsiyenti, tasodifiy og'ishlar ta'sir etuvchi omil, Fisher mezon, natijaviy omil, ishlab chiqarish, go'sht ishlab chiqarish, sut ishlab chiqarish.

Abstract. This article analyzes the costs of milk and meat production in the Samarkand region in 2006-2022, veterinary services, wages, costs per unit of feed econometric models. Theoretically and practically, the influence of these factors on the production of milk and meat has been studied, as well as a model of the relationship between their interaction has been constructed and the optimal option has been selected.

Keywords: regression, correlation coefficient, random deviations influencing factor, Fisher criterion, consequential factor, production, meat production, milk production.

KIRISH

Prezidentning 07.06.2022 yildagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020-2030 yillarga mo‘ljallangan strategiyasida belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini samarali tashkil etishga doir qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida” gi qarori qabul qilindi. Qaror Prezidentning 2019 yil 23-oktyabrdagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020-2030 yillarga mo‘ljallangan strategiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi PF-5853-son hamda 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi “2022-2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi PF-60-son Farmonlari ijrosini ta‘minlash maqsadida qabul qilindi.

Hujjat bilan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020-2030 yillarga mo‘ljallangan strategiyasida belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini samarali tashkil etishga doir qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar dasturi tasdiqlandi. Qishloq xo‘jaligi vazirligi muassisligida Qo‘qon oziq-ovqat texnologiyasi va muhandisligi xalqaro instituti tashkil etiladi va unga xalqaro ta‘lim standartlari darajasidagi xalqaro bozorlarda tan olingan sifat standartlarini (Global G.A.P, Organic, HACCP va boshqalar) joriy etishga qodir yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlash vazifasi yuklatiladi. Har bir hududda kamida bittadan agrologistika markazlari barpo etiladi va ularda xalqaro bozorlarda tan olingan sifat sertifikatlarini olish imkoniyati yaratiladi¹.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI

Qishloq xo‘jalik mahsulotlari, xususan chorvachilik mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish haqida mahalliy va chet el olimlari tomonidan ilmiy-tekshirish va ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan. Xorij olimlari Svi Grillixes, I.Tinbergen, V.N. Afanasev, S.A. Ayvazyan, A.M.Gataulin, N.M.Goreyeva, T.A.Dubrova, L.N.Demidova, O.P.Krastin, N.Sh.Kremer, N.P.Tixomirov, I.I.Yeliseyeva, Ye.M.Chetirkin va boshqalarning ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari muhim ahamiyat ega. Respublikamizda optimallashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha tadqiqot ishlari olib borishgan olimlaridan S.S.G‘ulomov, B.Yu.Xodiyev, B.A.Begalov, B.Berkinov, T.Sh.Shodiyev, Yo.Abdullayev, N.B.Ashurova, S.K.Salayev, N.Q. Murodova, I.S.Abdullayev va boshqalar sanoat va qishloq xo‘jalik mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishni ekonometrik va iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish hamda prognozlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha tizimli ilmiy izlanishlar olib borishmoqda.

¹Саодат Усманова. Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалигини ривожлантиришнинг 2020-2030 йилларга мўлжалланган стратегиянинг йўналишлари кенгайтирилди

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Ilmiy abstraksiya, kuzatish, qiyoslash, korrelyasion-regression tahlil.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

a) go'sht ishlab chiqarish. Dastlabki ma'lumotlar sifatida Samarqand viloyatining dehqon fermer xo'jaliklari o'n olti yil bo'yicha go'sht ishlab chiqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar sifatida 4 xil asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini olamiz, u holda regressiya tenglamasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\tilde{y}_1 = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_3 + a_4x_4; (1)$$

$$\tilde{y}_2 = b_0 + b_1 \ln(x_1) + b_2 \ln(x_2) + b_3 \ln(x_3) + b_4 \ln(x_4); (2)$$

$$\tilde{y} = c_0 \cdot c_1^{x_1} \cdot c_2^{x_2} \cdot c_3^{x_3} \cdot c_4^{x_4}; (3)$$

bunda,

\tilde{y} - go'sht ishlab chiqarish, tonna;

x_1 - go'sht narxi, tonna ming so'm;

x_2 - veterinariya xizmatlari, mln. so'm;

x_3 - ish haqi, ming so'm;

x_4 - oziqa birligi uchun qilingan xarajatlar, tonna ming so'mda;

a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 - hozircha noma'lum bo'lgan regressiya koeffitsiyentlari.

1-jadval

Samarqand viloyatining xo'jaliklari o'n yillar bo'yicha go'sht ishlab chiqarish²

No	yillar	y, tonna	Go'sht narxi, tonna-ming sum, x_1	veterinariya xizmati, ming.so'm, x_2	ish haqi, ming so'mda, x_3	Oziqa birligi uchun qilingan xarajatlar, ming so'mda, x_4
1	2010	179853	759257	45	8000	20045
2	2011	191764	862528	45	8000	20063
3	2012	203783	930089	45	8000	20078
4	2013	214254	994389	45	8000	20087
5	2014	229988	1064584	50	8500	25076
6	2015	244412	1132310	50	8500	25090
7	2016	257958	1228306	50	9000	25230
8	2017	262784	1240896	55	9000	30234
9	2018	294647	1241843	60	9500	30564
10	2019	297332	1273938	65	9500	35450
11	2020	285998,1	1307294	75	1000	35000
12	2021	305269	1337091	78	12300	43900
13	2022	314744	1371194	81	14600	51500

Go'sht ishlab chiqarish masalasini regression-korrelyasion tahlil qilamiz. Buning uchun kompyuter dasturlaridan biri Microsofft Excel elektron prossesoridan foydalanamiz.

I. $\tilde{y}_1 = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_3 + a_4x_4$ regressiya uchun hisoblashlarni Excel dasturida bajaramiz.

Koeffusiyenlar:

$a_0=$	-59774
$a_1=$	0,189041
$a_2=$	2758,436

²<https://samstat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/agriculture-2>-Samarqand viloyati statistika bosqarmasi ma'lumotlari (of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2023 year. Data of the statistical Directorate of the Samarkand region)

$$a_3 = 3,684234$$
$$a_4 = -3,13676$$

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_1 = -59774 + 0,189041x_1 + 2758,436x_2 + 3,684234x_3 - 3,684234x_4$$

2) Student mezonni hisoblangan qiymatilar:

$$t_0 = -1,303444777$$
$$t_1 = 7,351061679$$
$$t_2 = 1,804494598$$
$$t_3 = 1,698900649$$
$$t_4 = -1,291523412$$

Jadval qiymati = STYUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8) = 2,306004.

3) Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$F = 78,03073$; Jadval qiymati = F.OBP.PIX(0,05;4;8) = 3,83.

4) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,987426
Determinasiya siya koeffusiyenti R-квadrat	0,97501
Normal R-квadrat	0,962514
Standart xato	8850,839
Kuzatishlar	13

II. $\tilde{y}_2 = b_0 + b_1 \ln(x_1) + b_2 \ln(x_2) + b_3 \ln(x_3) + b_4 \ln(x_4)$ regressiya uchun

hisoblashlarni Excel dasturida bajaramiz.

Koeffusiyenlar:

$$b_0 = -2217977$$
$$b_1 = 172628,9$$
$$b_2 = 178579,7$$
$$b_3 = 13883,44$$
$$b_4 = -75817,6$$

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_2 = -2217977 + 172628,9 \ln(x_1) + 178579,7 \ln(x_2) +$$
$$+ 13883,44 \ln(x_3) - 75817,6 \ln(x_4)$$

2) Student mezonni hisoblangan qiymatilar:

$$t_0 = -8,236411359$$
$$t_1 = 5,959143648$$
$$t_2 = 1,954129415$$
$$t_3 = 1,855561826$$
$$t_4 = -1,051675526$$

Jadval qiymati = STUDENT.BR.2X(0,05;8) = 2,306004.

3)Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$$F = 88,31937; \text{ Jadval qiymati } = F.OBR.PX(0,05;4;8) = 3,83.$$

4) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,988866
Determinasiya siya koeffusiyenti	
R-квadrat	0,977856
Normal R-квadrat	0,966785
Standart xato	8331,485
Kuzatishlar	13

III. $\tilde{y} = c_0 \cdot x_1^{c_1} \cdot x_2^{c_2} \cdot x_3^{c_3} \cdot x_4^{c_4}$ regressiya uchun hisoblashlarni Excel dasturida bajaramiz.

Koeffusiyenlar:

$c_0 =$	0,4935949
$c_1 =$	0,815650795
$c_2 =$	0,600964091
$c_3 =$	0,047656376
$c_4 =$	-0,284829795

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_3 = 0,49 + 0,81 \ln(x_1) + 0,6 \ln(x_2) + 0,047 \ln(x_3) - 0,28 \ln(x_4).$$

Bu regressiya tenglamasini quyidagi ko`rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\tilde{y}_3 = 10^{0,49} \cdot x_1^{0,81} \cdot x_2^{0,6} \cdot x_3^{0,047} \cdot x_4^{-0,028}$$

yoki

$$\tilde{y}_3 = 3,09 \cdot x_1^{0,81} \cdot x_2^{0,6} \cdot x_3^{0,047} \cdot x_4^{-0,028}.$$

2)Styudent mezonni hisoblangan qiymatilar:

$t_0 =$	1,133164976
$t_1 =$	7,559625952
$t_2 =$	1,76561329
$t_3 =$	1,710114886
$t_4 =$	-1,060774513

Jadval qiymati =STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004.

3)Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$$F = 107,8113; \text{ Jadval qiymati } = F.OBR.IIX(0,05;4;8) = 3,83.$$

4) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,990851625
Determinasiya koeffusiyenti R- квадрат	0,981786942
Normal R-квадрат	0,972680413
Standart xato	0,013476618
Kuzatishlar	13

Endi sut ishlab chiqarish masalasini regression-korrelyasion tahlil qilamiz.

b) sut ishlab chiqarish. Masalani Samarqand viloyati fermer xo'jaliklarining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari asosida 2010-2022 yillarda sut yetishtirish misollarida qaraymiz. Ma'lumotlar quyidagi jadvalda ketirilgan.

Samarqand viloyati xo'jaliklari yillar bo'yicha sut ishlab chiqarish

2-jadval

№	Yillar	y, tonna	Sut narxi, tonna- ming sum	Veterinariya xizmati, ming.so`m	Ish haqi, ming so`mda	Oziqa birligi uchun qilingan xarajatlar, tonna ming so`mda
1	2010	759257	8767	1540,4	579	1390
2	2011	862528	7654	1569,3	591	1480
3	2012	930089	7865	1678,7	692	1460
4	2013	994389	7975	1717,7	638	1590
5	2014	1064584	7868	1743,7	645	1430
6	2015	1132310	8767	1567,7	654	1420
7	2016	1228306	1645	1751,3	650	1450
8	2017	1240896	1770	1234,8	650	1500
9	2018	1241843	2038	1311,1	650	2000
10	2019	1273938	2564	1450,4	700	2500
11	2020	1307294	3802	1567,1	710	2600
12	2021	1337091	3820	1687,5	740	2800
13	2022	1371194	4130	1769,1	760	2900

Dehqon xo'jaliklarda sut ishlab chiqarishni bashoratlash masalasini qaraymiz. Dastlabki ma'lumotlar sifatida Samarqand viloyatining dehqon fermer xo'jaliklari yillar bo'yicha sut ishlab chiqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar sifatida 4 xil asosiy servis xizmati ko'rsatkichlarini olamiz, u holda regressiya tenglamasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\tilde{y} = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_3 + a_4x_4,$$

bunda,

\tilde{y} - sut ishlab chiqarish, tonna;

x_1 – sut narxi, tonna ming so`m;

x_2 – veterinariya xizmatlari, mln. so`m;

x_3 – ish haqi, ming so`m;

x_4 – oziqa birligi uchun qilingan xarajatlar, tonna ming so`mda;

a_0, a_1, a_3, a_4 – hozircha noma'lum bo`lgan regressiya koeffitsiyentlari.

$$\tilde{y}_4 = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_3 + a_4x_4 \quad (4) \text{ regressiya uchun hisoblashlarni Excel}$$

dasturida bajaramiz.

1)Koeffusiyenlar:

$a_0=$	-1629,908798
$a_1=$	-35,54674589
$a_2=$	-33,99464581
$a_3=$	2048,868029
$a_4=$	6,708230868

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_4 = -1629,909 - 35,547x_1 - 33,995x_2 + 2048,868x_3 + 6,708x_4$$

) Styudent mezoni hisoblangan qiymatilari:

$t_0=$	-0,003384108
$t_1=$	-2,928104699
$t_2=$	-0,176785705
$t_3=$	2,130116046
$t_4=$	0,082997222

Jadval qiymati =STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004.

3)Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$F= 12,87516$; Jadval qiymati =F.OBP.IIX(0,05;4;8)=3,83.

4) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,930348161
Determinasiya koeffusiyenti R-квadrat	0,8655477
Normal R-квadrat	0,798321551
Standart xato	87839,36169
Kuzatishlar	13

II. $\tilde{y}_5 = b_0 + b_1 \ln(x_1) + b_2 \ln(x_2) + b_3 \ln(x_3) + b_4 \ln(x_4)$ regressiya uchun

hisoblashlarni Excel dasturida bajaramiz.

1)Koeffusiyenlar:

$b_0=$	-6883887,146
$b_1=$	-333362,5154
$b_2=$	-81383,7635
$b_3=$	3138823,786

$$b_4 = 195151,9928$$

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_5 = -6883887,146 - 333362,5154 \ln(x_1) - 81383,7635 \ln(x_2) + 3138823,786 \ln(x_3) + 195151,99281 \ln(x_4) \quad (5)$$

2) Student mezonini hisoblangan qiymatilar:

$t_0 =$	-2,500347986
$t_1 =$	-2,92396658
$t_2 =$	-0,12523864
$t_3 =$	2,35501616
$t_4 =$	0,577941349

Jadval qiymati = STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8) = 2,306004.

3) Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$F = 13,99261$; Jadval qiymati = F.OBP.IX(0,05;4;8) = 3,83.

) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,935383467
Determinasiya siya koeffusiyenti R-квadrat	0,87494223
Normal R-квadrat	0,812413345
Standart xato	84715,01532
Kuzatishlar	13

III. $\tilde{y}_6 = c_0 \cdot x_1^{c_1} \cdot x_2^{c_2} \cdot x_3^{c_3} \cdot x_4^{c_4}$ regressiya uchun hisoblashlarni Excel dasturida bajaramiz.

Koeffusiyenlar:

$c_0 =$	2,553188
$c_1 =$	-0,13795
$c_2 =$	-0,04647
$c_3 =$	1,440178
$c_4 =$	0,025215

Demak,

$$\tilde{y}_6 = 2,5 - 0,138 \ln(x_1) - 0,138 \ln(x_2) + 1,44 \ln(x_3) + 0,025 \ln(x_4).$$

Bu regressiya tenglamasini quyidagi ko`rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\tilde{y}_6 = 10^{2,5} \cdot x_1^{-0,138} \cdot x_2^{-0,138} \cdot x_3^{1,4} \cdot x_4^{0,024};$$

yoki

$$\tilde{y}_6 = 316,23 \cdot x_1^{-0,138} \cdot x_2^{-0,138} \cdot x_3^{1,4} \cdot x_4^{0,024}.$$

2) Student mezonini hisoblangan qiymatilar:

$t_0 =$	2,077382491
$t_1 =$	-2,710485919
$t_2 =$	-0,160175456

$$t_3 = 2,420527808$$

$$t_4 = 0,167279774$$

Jadval qiymati =STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004.

3) Fisher mezonining hisoblangan qiymati:

$F = 11,62199$; Jadval qiymati =F.OBR.PX(0,05;4;8)=3,83.

4) Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti:

Korrelyasiya koeffusiyenti R	0,923677
Determinasiya siya koeffusiyenti R-квadrat	0,853179
Normal R-квadrat	0,779768
Standart xato	0,037818
Kuzatishlar	13

a) go`sht ishlab chiqarish.

1) $\tilde{y}_1 = -59774 + 0,189041x_1 + 2758,436x_2 + 3,684234x_3 - 3,684234x_4$ regressiya tenglamasida $a_0 = -59774$; $a_1 = 0,189041$; $a_2 = 2758,436$; $a_3 = 3,684234$; $a_4 = -3,684234$ parametrlar Student mezoni bo`yicha $t_0 = -1,3$; $t_1 = 7,35$; $t_2 = 1,8$; $t_3 = 1,7$; $t_4 = -1,29$ ni baholashda $t_{a_i} > t_{jad}$ bajarilsa, parametrlar ahamiyatli bo`ladi.

Bu yerda Jadval qiymati =STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004 $> t_{a_i}$ ($i=0,1,2,3,4$) ekanligidan a_0 ; a_1 ; a_2 ; a_3 ; a_4 parametrlar muhim emas. Fisher mezoniga ko`ra $F_{his} > F_{jad}$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasini muhimligi kelib chiqadi. $F_{his} = 12,87516 > F_{jad} = 3,83$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasi muhim.

$$2) \tilde{y}_2 = -2217977 + 172628,9 \ln(x_1) + 178579,7 \ln(x_2) + 13883,44 \ln(x_3) - 75817,6 \ln(x_4)$$

regressiya tenglamasida

$$a_0 = -2217977; a_1 = 172628,9; a_2 = 178579,7; a_3 = 13883,44; a_4 = -75817,6$$

parametrlar Student mezoni bo`yicha $t_0 = -8,24$; $t_1 = 5,96$; $t_2 = 1,95$; $t_3 = 1,85$; $t_4 = -1,05$ ni baholashda $t_{a_i} > t_{jad}$ bajarilsa, parametrlar ahamiyatli bo`ladi.

Bu yerda Jadval qiymati =STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004 $> t_{a_i}$ ($i=0,1,2,3,4$) ekanligidan a_0 ; a_1 ; a_2 ; a_3 ; a_4 parametrlar muhim emas. Fisher mezoniga ko`ra $F_{his} > F_{jad}$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasini muhimligi kelib chiqadi. $F_{his} = 12,87516 > F_{jad} = 3,83$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasi muhim va.k.

b) sut ishlab chiqarish.

1) $\tilde{y}_1 = -1629,909 - 35,547x_1 - 33,995x_2 + 2048,868x_3 + 6,708x_4$ regressiya tenglamasida $a_0 = -1629,909$; $a_1 = -35,547$; $a_2 = -33,995$; $a_3 = 2048,868$; $a_4 = 6,708$ parametrlar Student mezoni bo`yicha $t_0 = -0,0034$; $t_1 = -2,928$; $t_2 = -0,177$; $t_3 = 2,13$;

$t_4=0,083$ ni baholashda $t_{i>t_{jad}}$ bajarilsa, parametrlar ahamiyatli bo`ladi.

Bu yerda Jadval qiymati = $STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004 > t_{a_i}$ ($i=0,1,2,3,4$) ekanligidan $a_0; a_1; a_2; a_3; a_4$ parametrlar muhim emas. Fisher mezoniga ko`ra $F_{his} > F_{jad}$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasini muhimligi kelib chiqadi. $F_{his} = 12,87516 > Jadval\ qiymati = F.OBR.IIX(0,05;4;8)=3,83$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasi muhim.

$$2) \tilde{y}_2 = -6883887,146 - 333362,51 \ln(x_1) - 81383,76 \ln(x_2) + 3138823,78 \ln(x_3) + 195151,99 \ln(x_4)$$

regressiya tenglamasida

$$a_0 = -6883887,146; a_1 = -333362,5154; a_2 = -81383,76;$$

$$a_3 = 3138823,786; a_4 = 195151,99281$$

parametrlar Student mezon bo`yicha $t_0 = -2,5; t_1 = -2,9; t_2 = -0,12; t_3 = 2,35; t_4 = 0,58$ ni baholashda $t_{i>t_{jad}}$ bajarilsa, parametrlar ahamiyatli bo`ladi.

Bu yerda Jadval qiymati = $STUDENT.OBR.2X(0,05;8)= 2,306004 > t_{a_i}$ ($i=0,1,2,3,4$) ekanligidan $a_0; a_1; a_2; a_3; a_4$ parametrlar muhim emas. Fisher mezoniga ko`ra $F_{his} > F_{jad}$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasini muhimligi kelib chiqadi. Aks holda muhim. $F_{his} = 12,87516 > Jadval\ qiymati = F.OBR.IIX(0,05;4;8)=3,83$ ekanligidan regressiya tenglamasi muhim va.k.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Xulosa qilib aytganda, go`sht mahsuloi ishlab chiqarish natijalarga ko`ra ekonometrik tahlil yordamida

$$1) \tilde{y}_1 = -59774 + 0,189041x_1 + 2758,436x_2 + 3,684234x_3 - 3,684234x_4$$

$$2) \tilde{y}_2 = -2217977 + 172628,9 \ln(x_1) + 178579,7 \ln(x_2) + 13883,44 \ln(x_3) - 75817,6 \ln(x_4)$$

$$3) \tilde{y}_3 = 3,09 \cdot x_1^{0,81} \cdot x_2^{0,6} \cdot x_3^{0,047} \cdot x_4^{-0,028} \quad \text{modellardan eng muhimi}$$

$\tilde{y}_2 = -2217977 + 172628,9 \ln(x_1) + 178579,7 \ln(x_2) + 13883,44 \ln(x_3) - 75817,6 \ln(x_4)$ ekanligi aniqlandi.

Chorvachilikda sut mahsuloi ishlab chiqarish natijalarga ko`ra ekonometrik tahlil yordamida

$$1) \tilde{y}_4 = -1629,909 - 35,547x_1 - 33,995x_2 + 2048,868x_3 + 6,708x_4$$

$$2) \tilde{y}_5 = -6883887,146 - 333362,5154 \ln(x_1) - 81383,7635 \ln(x_2) + 3138823,786 \ln(x_3) + 195151,99281 \ln(x_4)$$

$$3) \tilde{y}_6 = 316,23 \cdot x_1^{-0,138} \cdot x_2^{-0,138} \cdot x_3^{1,4} \cdot x_4^{0,024} \quad \text{modellardan eng muhimi}$$

$\tilde{y}_5 = -6883887,15 - 333362,51 \cdot \ln(x_1) - 81383,76 \cdot \ln(x_2) + 3138823,79 \cdot \ln(x_3) + 195151,99 \cdot \ln(x_4)$
ekanligi aniqlandi.

Korrelyatsion tahlil qilinib natijaviy omillar bilan unga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning zichligi korrelyatsiya koeffitsiyentini hisoblash orqali aniqlandi. Regression tahlil t-Student mezoni va F-Fisher mezoni bilan regressiya tenglamalari ichidan eng muhimlari tanlab olindi.

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